

Bias in the Research Lifecycle: Model and Guidelines

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Overview

The Lifecycle Model and Guidelines component provides structured guidance for addressing bias throughout the dataset creation process. It offers a practical, workflow-oriented approach to dealing with bias in dataset creation.

Structure and Content

This document provides guidelines for tasks that feature throughout the dataset lifecycle. It is organised into five key stages¹:

1. **Set Up:** Project conceptualisation, planning, and funding
2. **Collection:** Gathering and organising relevant data
3. **Process:** Preparing data for analysis
4. **Analyse:** Exploring relationships and patterns in the data
5. **Preserve & Share:** Publishing, preserving, and contextualising the dataset

Each stage starts with a recommendation for what actions to take and what to include in your documentation for that part of the dataset creation. Each task includes expressions of biases to consider through questions, recommended actions to take, and resources to aid you in articulating bias in your work.

Please note, the tasks, considerations, and good practices are in no particular order.

Documentation

We strongly recommend documenting your process through each of the questions and actions outlined in this framework. Each stage of the lifecycle includes a ‘recommended documentation’ section to ensure methodological rigor and transparency. This documentation should be published and openly available for future reference and audit.

Comprehensive Data Documentation Good documentation should detail how data is curated: who collected it and when, the collection methodology, funding sources, and how data was reused, integrated, or preprocessed. Include any limitations or known biases in original sources and document your team’s rationale for key decisions. This transparency addresses the crisis of shared understanding around bias across disciplines and helps identify both discrimination (unfair treatment or representation) and opacity (obscured processes or perspectives).

Implementation Framework The guidelines provide concrete steps that researchers can implement at each stage of their work. By following this structured approach, teams can systematically identify and address biases that might otherwise go unnoticed until later stages of the research process. Document your bias mitigation strategies using a **Good-Better-Best** approach that outlines progressive strategies based on available resources. We recommend creating your own schema (see [template](#)) that aligns with your research project—

¹ This model builds upon Research Data Alliance (July 2024), *The creation of a harmonised research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to existing models*. https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/D1_The-creation-of-a-harmonised-research-data-lifecycle-RDL-model-and-crosswalk-to-existing-models-.pdf.

this process helps teams collectively identify and discuss project-specific biases while contributing to shared methodological understanding across the research community.

Relationship to Other Components

While the [Bias Vocabulary](#) examines bias expressions conceptually, this Lifecycle Model takes a process-oriented approach, integrating bias considerations directly into standard dataset creation workflows. Together, these components provide both theoretical understanding and practical implementation strategies.

Limitations

We acknowledge that we will inadvertently have missed certain considerations of bias, as well as forms of bias as they appear in other fields, such as cognitive biases. This overview is not intended to be - nor should it be interpreted as - conclusive or comprehensive. For any queries, comments or feedback, please feel free to [contact us](#).

1 – Set Up

Description: During **Set up**, the research is conceptualised, planned and funded. This stage highlights the environment in which dataset creation will happen, as the research question, mission and values will be defined and data collection practices outlined. At this stage, you are thinking about dataset creation as a potential method and/or output for your research, but are not actively undertaking creation yet - this stage merely sets the scene for it.

Recommended documentation

Describe your project beginnings

- Write your [Data Management Plan](#), [Ethical Commitments](#) and [Mission Statement](#)
 - Document your answers to questions regarding project conceptualisation. This will both be a guide as well as a place of reflection throughout your research.
-

Tasks

Identify a Research Topic

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Positionality

- How does the social, political, economic, cultural, academic context you are embedded in impact your choice of research?
- Are there policies/guidelines within your institution that are relevant to your project – if so, which ones?²

Silences

- What gaps exist in current research?
- What gaps are you trying to fill in your research? Time period, geography, actors, concepts?
- What is your primary source data and what are its advantages and shortcomings?

Representation

- Who is represented in the scholarship and sources that are used? And who is not represented?

Impact

- Who do the scholarship and/or research projects currently impact positively and/or negatively, and in what way? In terms of accessibility (digital divide), representation, use of language?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Reflect on these questions as part of project conceptualization.

² Adapted from Dataschool Utrecht, [DEDA Dataschool](#) (2022).

- Document discussions held, research done and decisions made for future reference.
- Have your research be led by social justice values and positive societal impact - however your project may define these.³
- Ensure your research question(s) are shaped by the availability and content of sources. Heavily biased sources can be the best resources for one research question, but totally unfit to answer another.

Resources

Further websites with helpful guiding questions and toolkits to consider *before* the start of your research:

- Data Ethics Decision Aid: <https://deda.dataschool.nl/en/>
- USC Libraries, *Inclusive and Responsible Dataset Usage*: <https://libguides.usc.edu/inclusive-datasets/considerations>
- University of Bath, *Research Data Service Homepage: Research Data Home*: <https://library.bath.ac.uk/research-data>
- RDMkit, *Ethical aspects*: <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/ethics#which-aspects-of-rdm-might-raise-ethical-issues>
- Always Already Computational - Collections as Data. 50 things you can do: <https://collectionsasdata.github.io/fiftythings/>

Write Funding Proposals

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Positionality

- How does the social, political, economic, cultural, academic context you are embedded in impact what topics of research are receiving funding? In what way are you aligning your research to this?
- Does your institution have in-house expertise on writing successful funding proposals? How does this impact your position?

Recruitment

- Will your recruitment practices be inclusive?

Collaboration

- In what way could you work with affected communities?
- In what way could you collaborate with specialist academics/researchers to mitigate potential biases in your research?

Representation

³ Adapted from Educational Innovation Erasmus University Rotterdam, [Positionality](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

- Who is and who is not represented in your research funding outline?

Impact

- Who would your research impact positively and/or negatively, and in what way? In terms of agenda, accessibility (digital divide), representation, use of language?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Include ethical considerations into your proposal, whether or not this is asked for. Show the funding agency that alongside their own mission, ethical considerations are necessary and urgent to think about.
- Speak about how will you allocate money to the combatting of bias (e.g. extra personnel, part of research is on ethics issues, pot of money for collaboration, widen theme of research or source base as an attempt to combat bias)
- Actively pursue the allocation of money to collaborate with affected communities. Ensure enough money is set aside for all aspects of community engagement (monetary remuneration for expertise; cultivating sense of community between collaborators/citizen scientists⁴). Also consider whether you can create sustainable networks that will contribute to the setting up of future projects.
- Focus on the creation of a diverse and inclusive project and team.

Resources

- Loughborough University, [Embedding EDI in Grant Proposals](#). Version: Feb 2023
- Maastricht University, [How to Address Diversity in Research Proposals - A Guide](#).

Write a Data Management Plan (DMP)

Description: A DMP is a roadmap for good data management at every stage of research. It is a **living** document that will reflect changes and updates made to your research.

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

FAIR

- How do you plan to publish FAIR data?
- Do you foresee any issues with aligning your project with the FAIR principles? Why?

Impact

- In what way would your data harm other persons and the environment?⁵

Ownership

- Who (legally) owns the data you will produce?
- How will you acknowledge data contributors and sources?

⁴ For example, as [Historical Database of Suriname en the Caribbean](#) (HDSC) have done.

⁵ Adapted from RDMkit, [Ethical aspects](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

Durability

- How will you ensure your data remains FAIR in the future, after the project ends?
- What preservation strategies will you implement for long-term accessibility?
- Who will maintain the dataset once the project ends?

Privacy

- How will your research data be stored safely? Is there need for anonymisation?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Follow online guidelines/templates for writing DMPs. Your institute may already have a template/guidelines that you can use.
- Use your envisioned dataset documentation templates to guide writing your DMP. This ensures dataset documentation is considered throughout the dataset creation process and allows for more efficient documentation.
 - This ensures your DMP includes details on version control practices and proposed usages of the created dataset.
 - Examples of dataset documentation are [data-envelopes](#) and [datasheets \(for cultural heritage\)](#).
- Use the [FAIR Implementation Profile](#) questionnaire to guide writing your DMP, specifically with regards to what specifications to consider to make your dataset FAIR compliant.
- Include how harm to other beings and the environment can be identified and mitigated in a timely manner.⁶
- Include versioning into your DMP to encourage regular re-evaluation during the project.

Resources

Take a look at your institutional (faculty, department) guidelines and/or Code of Conducts regarding DMPs. Below are external resources that may be helpful:

- DMP tool (for filling out templates of various funding institutions): <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>
 - Examples of DMP templates: <https://www.lib4ri.ch/research-data-management-resources>
- Resource for best practices for Data Management: <https://campus.dariah.eu/resources/pathfinders/dariah-pathfinder-to-data-management-best-practices-in-the-humanities>
- FAIR: <https://www.go-fair.org/>
 - FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs): <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

⁶ Adapted from RDMkit, [Ethical aspects](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

- Alignment FIPs to DMPs: Singh et al. (2025). *Aligning Data Management Plans with Community Standards Using FAIR Implementation Profiles*. In: Sfakakis, M., Garoufallou, E., Damigos, M., Salaba, A., Papatheodorou, C. (eds) *Metadata and Semantic Research*. MTSR 2024. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 2331. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-81974-2_14 (co-authored by Angelica Maineri and Shuai Wang).
- Data documentation:
 - Data-envelopes for Cultural Heritage: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.legal-1.9/>
 - Datasheets for Cultural Heritage: <https://openhumanitiesdata.metajnl.com/articles/10.5334/johd.124>
 - AI Model Research Documentation Sheet (AIRDocS): <https://zenodo.org/records/14550113>
 - The checklist for Collections as Data from the GlamLABS Community: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/gkmc-06-2023-0195/full/html>
 - Datasheets at DRI: https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/8c980k93k#dri_download_modal_id
 - Datasheets for Web Archive: <https://blogs.bl.uk/webarchive/2024/11/datasheets-for-web-archives-toolkit-is-now-live.html>
 - Quality Measures for Datasets: <https://datanutrition.org/labels/>

Write Ethical Commitments

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Positionality

- How does the social, political, economic, cultural, academic context you are embedded in relate to advancing social justice?
 - Are you conducting research from a position of historical privilege? (For example, are you based in a former colonial power studying colonized regions?) How can you then use the benefits of your context to advance the deconstruction of existing power structures?

Transparency

- Do you have any ethical concerns about the research? Think of:
 - What accessibility barriers might your research create or reinforce?
 - How might your research methodologies perpetuate existing inequalities?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Use the format: *We acknowledge [injustice]. We are committed to [action to lessen the burden of injustice]*. This provides a succinct overview for readers to know what you stand for and how your actions will reflect this.⁷

⁷ See for reference: On These Grounds, [Ethical Commitments](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

- Include your gut-feelings about the project, including concerns.⁸
- Add positionality statements to your Ethical Commitments, clearly communicating to your audience your awareness of the context you work in and what you benefit from.⁹
- Include versioning into your Ethical Commitments to encourage regular re-evaluation during the project.

Resources

Examples of Ethical Commitments:

- Globalise: <https://docs.globalise.huygens.knaw.nl/ethics/policy/>
- Enslaved.org: <https://enslaved.org/statementofEthics/>
- On these Grounds: <https://onthesegrounds.org/s/OTG/page/ethical-commitments>

Write a Mission Statement

Description: A mission statement articulates your project's purpose, values, and approach. It serves as both an internal compass and a public declaration of your research intentions, ethical stance, and expected outcomes.

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Transparency

- How active will your intervention be?
- Who will your research impact positively/negatively?
- What is the proposed outcome of the research? Could there be unintended uses and/or consequences?
- What values drive your work and how are they reflected in your work?
- Are there any accessibility restrictions?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Reflect on all questions above and incorporate answers, ideas and concerns into your mission statement. This will ensure **expectation management** for collaborators and audiences.
- Outline values/research philosophy that drive your research.
 - For example: Community, Trust and Time, Knowledge (Co-)Production, Redistribution, Accountability, Interrogating Power, Imagination.¹⁰
- Discuss how active your ethical intervention will be.
 - For example: Contentious language will not be included as prelabels in published datasets,

⁸ Adapted from Dataschool Utrecht, [DEDA Dataschool](#) (2022).

⁹ From conversations with [Globalise](#); Kelly and Vicky Breemen, forthcoming publication.

¹⁰ Adapted from DAIR Institute, [Our Research Philosophy](#) (2022).

but will feature in public user interface (*Globalise*).

Contentious language will feature in public user interface, but with a caveat box providing context (*Slave Voyages*).

Contentious language will be retained for the historicity of sources, but alternative terms will be used to write about the sources (*Historical Database of Suriname and Caribbean*).

- Include any parts of your research that should be contextualised up front: use of contentious categories, naming, terms, and/or keywords; errors that may be found; choices for use of specific language over others.¹¹
- Outline predicted outputs.
- Outline imagined use of your research (data).
 - Also include imagined accessibility restrictions (e.g. data can only be accessed onsite, or with an account).
 - Also include restrictions, in terms of licensing.¹²
- Include ways for audiences (both academic and broader) to contact, engage with and/or provide feedback to the project.
- Include versioning into your Mission Statement to encourage regular re-evaluation during the project.
- Acknowledge that responsible research will always evolve, and is therefore never-ending (even after project end). Manage expectations regarding this in your mission statement.

Resources

Take a look at your institutional (faculty, department) guidelines and/or Code of Conducts regarding DMPs. Below are external resources that may be helpful:

Examples of Mission Statements:

- Globalise: https://docs.globalise.huygens.knaw.nl/mission/mission_researchthemes/
- One More Voice: https://onemorevoice.org/html/documents/mission_statement.html
- DAIR Institute: <https://www.dair-institute.org/research-philosophy/>
- Jaap Kunst Collection - Hearing the Indonesian Archipelago: <https://jaapkunst.org/about/>

¹¹ Adapted from Jaap Kunst Sound Collection, [Methodology](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

¹² Adapted from Jaap Kunst Sound Collection, [Uses](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

2 – Collection

Description: In the **Collect** stage, relevant data is collected and stored in the chosen organisational structure of the project, creating the content of the dataset. It builds on the Set Up stage, but also reflects and updates decisions made then.

Recommended documentation

Describe your collection process, metadata creation, contextualisation documentation.

- Include all considerations below each task.
 - Write about what types of sources and/or data you are creating the dataset from, their creators and historical context (provenance).
 - Revise outdated metadata of original source material.
 - Define and describe your categories and choices made to create them.
-

Tasks

Select and Curate Sources and/or Data

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Availability

- What sources are available (e.g. only written sources, no oral sources; only governmental reports, no personal histories)?
- In what way does a lack of availability of sources skew your dataset (e.g. do you only have data on certain communities and not others)?

Expertise

- What skills and expertise does your research team possess? How does this impact the sources/data you are able to work with and the ways in which you process this data (e.g. knowledge of paleography and language/cultural contexts or knowledge of a historical context might be necessary to work with certain kinds of sources)?

Accessibility

- What sources are accessible (e.g. not destroyed; in country; in language researcher understands, digitized and freely available online)?

Multivocality

- Does your data allow for the inclusion of multiple perspectives?
- What sources are you not collecting from - and would they provide different perspectives?
- How can you incorporate diverse viewpoints within your dataset?

Representation

- Which individuals, communities, or viewpoints are represented in your data?
- Which are absent or underrepresented?

- How might these representation patterns affect analysis and how will this be communicated to other users/visitors/researchers?

Historicity

- Did you modify the data from its original source?
- Are you using terms as they are in the source document (extraction/verbatim)? Or did you interpret content in the source document in order to capture the data point? e.g. Sex of a person can be explicitly stated in the document or interpreted by the data collector (through names, for example).
- How are you handling ambiguous elements like implied gender or social status?

Provenance

- Where does your data come from? What is the context of its creation/inheritance?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Document your collection process according to a documentation template chosen before, e.g. data-envelopes.
 - Include all the knowledge you possess about the data: its shortcomings and your collection practices and how you have modified the data (e.g. your data may not cover certain chronological periods; you may only have access to digitized files of certain types of archives; you may have normalised the spellings of concepts in your data which means that it cannot be used to research spelling variation of terms).
 - Include how you went about dealing with and adapting ambiguous/illegible information in the source.
- Outline your collection/selection criteria for sources.
 - Discuss the reasons justifying the exclusion/inclusion of research data in a particular context.
 - If you have learned something about your datasource that was not previously documented, be sure to make note of it such that you can convey it to future users of the dataset.
- Reflect on how your sources impact the (research) questions you ask.
 - And vice versa: what questions can you ask with the available sources?
- Critically assess your collection practices, in order to identify gaps and oversights.
- Critically assess the skills and expertise of your team.
- Actively pursue the inclusion of different perspectives – diversify your data.
 - Through e.g. use of different types of sources; different types of producers of sources; different provenances of sources; different interpretations
 - Involving communities or other specialists.
- Find complementary data sources to the ones you use to offer an alternative or wider perspective on the data.

- e.g. if you are working with VOC shipping lists, attempt to bring in shipping lists for the same period and region from other data sources to offer a fuller view of shipping data, and mitigate absences in each of the datasets.
- Really *know* your sources: conduct research into their provenance, the reason they were created, the author(s), the time period, its significance. Understanding the context of your sources allows you to ask the right questions.

Resources

- Hamed Taherdoost. **Data Collection Methods and Tools for Research**; A Step-by-Step Guide to Choose Data Collection Technique for Academic and Business Research Projects. International Journal of Academic Research in Management (IJARM), 2021, 10 (1), pp.10-38. <https://hal.science/hal-03741847/document>
- **GLAM Workbench**. [Finding GLAM Data](#).
- **OSF Support, How to Make a Data Dictionary**
 - Helps to create an overview with definitions for your categories.
- **Pressing Matter project**: <https://pressingmatter.nl/>
- **Background reading**:
 - Quinn, Brian. “Collection Development and the Psychology of Bias.” The Library Quarterly 82, no. 3 (2012): 277–304. <https://doi.org/10.1086/665933>.
 - Sander Molenaar, *Late Imperial China Special Issue*, forthcoming publication.
 - Sarah Binta Alam Shoilee, Annastiina Ahola, Heikki Rantala, Eero Hyvönen, Victor de Boer, Jacco van Ossenbruggen, and Susan Legene. “Enhancing Provenance Research with Linked Data: A Visual Approach to Knowledge Discovery.” SemDH’25: Second International Workshop of Semantic Digital Humanities, June 1-2 2025, Portoroz, Slovenia. <https://seco.cs.aalto.fi/publications/2025/shoilee-et-al-pm-sampo-2025.pdf>

Create Metadata for the Data

Description: This task refers to the metadata of individual parts of the data as well as the combined dataset. It also refers to a reflection on the original metadata of the source.

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Accuracy

- Is your metadata correct?
- Is the metadata of your source (data) correct?

Transparency

- What are you basing your metadata descriptions on?
- Is it clear how the original source (data) metadata was created?

Representation

- Are you providing consistent levels of detail across all descriptions? If not, what are the implications of this? And how will this be communicated to others?
- Does the metadata of your source (data) do so?

Multivocality

- Does your metadata fairly describe different perspectives that exist?
- Does the metadata of your source (data) do so?
- How does your metadata handle contested or evolving terminology?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- For technical metadata: use a metadata standard useful for your project - and adapt it to include all information you need. Using a metadata standard ensures consistency across research.¹³
 - Check the metadata standards of the repository you will use to store your research.
- Work with collaborators from diverse groups to accurately describe your data with the historical complexity it has.¹⁴
- When writing metadata: Focus on the humanity of an individual before their identity/ies, e.g. always mention names before saying their social status.¹⁵
- Avoid the use of passive voice when describing oppressive relationships.
- If, as a result of above considerations, the original source (data) metadata is not inclusive, transparent or factually incorrect (e.g. antiquated descriptions with outdated references to places and communities): consider how to improve these descriptions.
 - Convey actions taken in your documentation.
 - Share this information with the institutions that host the original data and metadata.

Resources

- Metadata standards: <https://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/standards/>
- Cornell Data Services, “Guide to writing “readme” style metadata”: <https://data.research.cornell.edu/data-management/sharing/readme/>
- University of Wisconsin-Madison, Five Ways to Document Your Data: <https://data.wisc.edu/data-literacy/document/>
- Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia, Anti-Racist Description Resources: https://archivesforblacklives.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/ardr_final.pdf

¹³ Adapted from Lib4RI, [Collecting](#) (accessed 27 August 2025).

¹⁴ Adapted from Archives for Black Lives, [Anti-Racist Description Resources](#) (2019), pp. 3-4.

¹⁵ Adapted from Archives for Black Lives, [Anti-Racist Description Resources](#) (2019), pp. 3-4.

- Harvard University, Guidelines for Inclusive and Conscientious
Description: <https://harvardwiki.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/hmschommanual/pages/49446971/Guidelines+for+Inclusive+and+Conscientious+Description>
- Fujimoto, Azuma, Toru Ogawa, Kazuyoshi Yamamoto, Yusuke Matsui, Toshihiko Yamasaki, and Kiyoharu Aizawa. “**Manga109 Dataset and Creation of Metadata.**” Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on coMics ANalysis, Processing and Understanding (New York, NY, USA), MANPU ’16, Association for Computing Machinery, December 4, 2016, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3011549.3011551>.
- Nesterov, A., Hollink, L., & van Ossenbruggen, J. (2025). **Alter Heritage: A web app to gather expert knowledge on inclusive cultural heritage metadata.** In International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management.
- Example documentation: **Globalise** [data-envelopes and historical contextualisation](#).

Create usable categories and variables for your dataset

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

FAIR

- Are your categories clearly defined and documented?
- Can your categories be linked to established ontologies?
- Do your categories support interoperability with other datasets?

Representation

- Be mindful of how these categories affect your research: does creating the category ‘ethnic category’ perpetuate the views of the colonial governments - and is this what you want in your research? What is its value and implications?
- How might users interpret or misinterpret your categories?

Multivocality

- Do your categories represent complex data adequately?
- Can your framework accommodate multiple perspectives/worldviews?

Historicity

- Are you using categories as used by your sources? If so, consider elaborating your choice of categories to your users.
- How do you balance historical accuracy with contemporary ethical considerations while avoiding presentism?¹⁶

Methodology (including algorithms)

- How might your category choices introduce or amplify bias in ML applications?
- Could your variables create problematic correlations or inferences when used in predictive models?
- How might simplifications in categorization lead to algorithmic discrimination?
- How might missing or unbalanced data within categories affect computational analysis?

¹⁶ With regards presentist bias, consider reading Manjusha Kuruppath’s blogpost: <https://combattingbias.huylgens.knaw.nl/news/historicalbias/>

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Look at other vocabularies out there (see *Resources*).
- Create and optimise your template for collecting data through the inclusion of usable categories and variables.
- Describe in documentation what each category/variable means.
- Base your categories on previously collected material and historical context. Do you know your data sources and existing research about these data sources well enough to know the strength and weaknesses of categories used in the data sources themselves?
- Create metadata flags for variables that require special handling in ML contexts.
- Test your categorisation with diverse stakeholders to identify unforeseen biases.¹⁷

Resources

Examples of vocabularies, thesauri, ontologies:

- **Globalise:**
 - Politics: <https://datasets.iisg.amsterdam/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=hdl:10622/SOS0KC>
 - Ethnicities, Religious Groups and Castes: <https://datasets.iisg.amsterdam/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=hdl:10622/5LRS03>
- **Exploring Slave Trade in Asia:** <https://exploringslavetradeinasia.com/documentation.php>
- **Enslaved.org:** <https://docs.enslaved.org/controlledVocabulary/>
- **Homosaurus:** <https://homosaurus.org/>
- **Unsilencing Colonial Archives:**
 - Taxonomy: https://github.com/budh333/UnSilence_VOC
 - Paper: <https://dare.uva.nl/search?identifier=87c624d7-165e-4df1-a15a-c8d8cc5d7b32>

Existing categorisations:

- **Museum cataloguing:** Government of Canada, Canadian Heritage. “Nomenclature for Museum Cataloging.” September 1, 2018. <https://page.nomenclature.info/apropos-about.app?lang=en>.
- **Biased gender language classification:** Havens, Lucy. “Towards Gender Biased Language Classification: A Case Study with British English Archival Metadata Descriptions.” Paper presented at NAACL-HLT. Student Research Workshop, 2022.

¹⁷ For example, the project Unsilencing Colonial Archives benefited hugely from critique on essentialism on their first version of the proposed taxonomy by archivists and historians from the Dutch National Archives and Het Nieuwe Instituut.

- **Taxonomy of Labour Relations:** Hofmeester, Karin; Lucassen, Jan; Lucassen, Leo; Stapel, Rombert; Zijdeman, Richard, 2016, “The Global Collaboratory on the History of Labour Relations, 1500-2000: Background, Set-Up, Taxonomy, and Applications”, <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/4OGRAD>, IISH Data Collection, V1

Background reading:

- Bowker, Geoffrey C., and Susan Leigh Star. *Sorting Things out: Classification and Its Consequences*. MIT press, 2000.

Reflect: Assess data storage structure of DMP

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Privacy

- Is the collected data stored safely?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- If necessary, reconsider your storage plans in the DMP and find alternatives.

Resources

See [Set up: Write Data Management Plan](#)

Reflect: Revisit your Set Up documentation

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Transparency

- Does the documentation reflect your current thinking in your research?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Update the living documents (DMP, Mission Statement, and Ethics Commitment) to reflect changes in research and thinking.
- Update the versioning of the documentation.

Resources

See [Set up](#)

3 – Process

Description: The **Process** stage aims to make the data ready for analysis. This includes pre-processing, cleaning, refining, reformatting, filtering, and conducting quality control of the collected data. This simultaneously creates a reusable and consistent dataset.

Recommended documentation

Describe your processing process.

- Include all considerations below each task.
- Write about what types of sources and/or data you are creating the dataset from, their creators and historical context (provenance).
- Revise outdated metadata of original source material.
- Define and describe your categories and choices made to create them.

Tasks

Annotate your data

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Accuracy

- How accurate are your annotations?

Transparency

- What are you basing your annotations on?

Multivocality

- Does your annotation represent diversity adequately?

Expertise

- Who is annotating your data? What is their expertise and how can this impact your data annotation?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Document your annotation practices and further processing workflow.
 - Include what technique and strategy your research uses for annotations.
 - Include what categories and variables have been used for data fields.
 - Include an explanation of significance of empty fields and meaning of any special value, if applicable.
 - Include an outline of all relationships between data fields (e.g. if a dataset contains “medication” and “disease”, is that medication actually used to treat the disease? Or is it a medication that the patient is using for other reasons?).¹⁸

¹⁸ Taken from RDMkit, [Processing](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

- Make use of an inter-annotation agreement (IAA).
- Work with communities and collaborators to ensure diversity of perspectives and accuracy of annotations.

Resources

Globalise:

- Background to annotation: <https://globalise.huygens.knaw.nl/automatic-event-detection-in-early-modern-dutch-voc-documents-the-annotation-phase/>
- Analysis of annotation: <https://globalise.huygens.knaw.nl/yes-okay-but-what-were-they-doing/>

HUB Global Labour Conflicts:

- van Kasteel, Teun; Aurich, Jens, 2024, “Amok Events in 19th Century Dutch Newspapers”, <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/0WWVWT>, IISH Data Collection, V4, UNF:6:YSefEtN1bDpqaOZ/lApgJg== [fileUNF]
- Läufer, Josephine; Aurich, Jens, 2024, “Desertion Events in 19th Century Dutch Newspapers”, <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/D6OXZ9>, IISH Data Collection, V3, UNF:6:PLqCWvjO39KGxxQhgp2J6w== [fileUNF]

Convert data into readable format¹⁹

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Harmful Language

- Does your data contain offensive/harmful language and/or categories?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Use ‘preferred’ and ‘alternative’ labels to distinguish offensive and usable terminology.
 - This flags to the computational model that certain words are not preferable, yet retains historicity.
- Making changes to data formats such that different datasets will be compatible for integration with each other.²⁰

Resources

Previous research to help identify harmful language:

DE-BIAS:

- Vocabulary: <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/the-de-bias-vocabulary>
- Identification tool: <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/the-de-bias-tool>

¹⁹ Taken from RDMkit, [Processing](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

²⁰ Taken from RDMkit, [Processing](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

- Knowledge Graph of Contentious Terminology
 Nesterov, A., Hollink, L., van Erp, M., van Ossenbruggen, J. (2023). A Knowledge Graph of Contentious Terminology for Inclusive Representation of Cultural Heritage. In: Pesquita, C., et al. The Semantic Web. ESWC 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13870. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-33455-9_30

Alternative vocabulary lists:

- Words Matter: <https://www.materialculture.nl/en/publications/words-matter>
- Transformative Arabic Language Guide: <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/beirut/22183-20250724.pdf>
- Inclusive Terminology Glossary: <https://culturalheritageterminology.co.uk/>
- Indigenous Peoples Terminology: <https://www.ictinc.ca/blog/indigenous-peoples-terminology-guidelines-for-usage>
- DEI Controlled Vocab
 List: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/19solOX6tQTYvIF4lr_JNz2WlcsA76CcK3bxvYZ8cHzg/edit?gid=0#gid=0
- Gender, Sex and Sexual Orientation: <https://gsso.research.cchmc.org/#!/> (ontology)
- Homosaurus: <https://homosaurus.org/> (linked data vocabulary)

Reflect: Reflect on the categories and variables used

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Representation

- Is there data that is unfairly represented by the used categories?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Rethink/add categories or find a new framework for your data so that it reflects your data accurately.

Resources

See [Collection: Create usable categories and variables for your dataset](#)

4 – Analyse

Description: The **Analyse** stage centres on exploring trends and relationships in your data. This can be done through creation of visualisations and/or statistical analysis.

Recommended documentation

Describe your analysis process and workflow.

- Include what tools, code and data were used to come to your analysis.²¹
 - Describe the shortcomings and benefits of your chosen form of analysis.
 - Outline other possible ways your data can be read and used, and whether or not the outcomes may be different.
-

Tasks

Analysing and Interpreting Data

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Unintended Use

- Can the visualisation/analysis be misinterpreted?²²

Representation

- What does the chosen visualisation style highlight and under- and/or misrepresent?²³

Reproducibility

- Have you documented your analysis process sufficiently for others to reproduce it?
- How are you handling intersectionality in your analysis?
- Do your interpretations risk essentializing complex identities?

Methodology (including algorithms)

- How might your analytical methods themselves introduce bias?
- What assumptions underlie your interpretive frameworks?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Document the shortcomings and possibilities of your analysis
 - Highlight these are not the only conclusions that can be drawn from your data, and describe other potential outcomes and uses.
 - Include different forms of visualisation, such as word-concept distance or statistics.
 - Develop strategies for communicating uncertainty alongside findings
-

²¹ Adapted from RDMkit, [Analysing](#) (accessed 21 August 2025).

²² Adapted from Dataschool Utrecht, [DEDA Dataschool](#) (2022).

²³ Adapted from Dataschool Utrecht, [DEDA Dataschool](#) (2022).

Resources

- Data Feminism <https://data-feminism.mitpress.mit.edu/>
 - Generous Interfaces for Digital Cultural Collections <https://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/9/1/000205/000205.html>
-

Reflect: Assess sufficiency of data collection

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Silences

- Are there gaps and/or silences in your data collection process?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Rethink your data collection practices. Adjust if needed.
 - Document decisions made in adjusting (or not adjusting) data collection practice.
 - Document implications of the data collection process on output and the subsequent use of the output.
-

Resources

See [Set Up: Select and Curate Sources and/or Data](#)

5 – Preserve & Share

Description: During **Preserve & Share**, the created and cleaned dataset is stored safely and sustainably, ensuring integrity and accessibility for the future. Furthermore, the data and documentation (and if relevant, findings) are published for external usage and availability.

Recommended documentation

Publish documentation and contextualisation on your dataset, adapting it to your intended audiences.

- Consider your audience: For academic audiences, publish extensive documentation for the sake of understandability and reproducibility. For broader audiences, publish the extensive documentation, but include different forms of presenting results and context as well (e.g. visualisations or short summaries).
- Use consistent formats, and publish in languages that allow for wider comprehensibility and usability. Ensure that the writing style is accessible.
- In any version of published documentation, prioritise context and documentation necessary for harmful consequences and/or misuse of the dataset to be mitigated.
- Highlight what *cannot* be found in your data, besides its value and possibilities.
- Avoid using passive voice when describing oppressive relationships.²⁴

Tasks

Contextualise data for external users

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Unintended Use

- Can the research data be misinterpreted?
- Or can the data be used for a different intended purpose (so-called *function creep*)?
- Can any information in your dataset be viewed as misleading?

Transparency

- If you identified gaps during the analysis process: how are you representing these to your audience?
 - For example, visualisations documentation, etc.
- What alternative resources that may address gaps/relevant topics to your research do you refer your users to?
 - Have/Can you link this data to other archives/data?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Refer and/or link to different resources that may address similar topics to your research.

²⁴ Adapted from Archives for Black Lives, [Anti-Racist Description Resources](#) (2019), pp. 3-4.

- Do not use softening language in presenting contentious pasts.²⁵
- Include historical and dataset creation process context, making the dataset itself, and choices made by your team clear to the users.
 - For example, see [Globalise's documentation](#).
- Include clear visualisations to make clear what is in your data.
 - For example: harmful language stats, category stats, uneven lengths of descriptions.
- “Evaluate local descriptive practices and policies using the criteria: Which audiences does this description center? Which audiences does it exclude? For academic archives, this could look like making description more comprehensible for undergraduates, genealogists/family historians, and local community members. For archives collecting Spanish-language material, this could mean considering whether English-language finding aids are serving users. This could also look like minimizing archival jargon.”²⁶

Resources

Examples of published visualisations:

- Slave Voyages: <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database#visualization>
- ESTA: <https://exploringslavetradeinasia.com/maps.php>
- Feral Atlas: <https://feralatlas.org>

Example of succinct format of showing (meta)data details:

- Quality Measures for Datasets: <https://datanutrition.org/labels/>
- Traditional Knowledge Labels: <https://localcontexts.org/labels/traditional-knowledge-labels/>
- Responsible Datasets in Context: <https://www.responsible-datasets-in-context.com/>

Create or choose an interface to publish data, analyses, visualisations and other publications

When undertaking this task, what should you consider?

Accessibility

- Who is included/excluded from data access and why?
- Does your interface consider the digital divide?

Ownership

²⁵ From conversations with [Historical Database of Suriname and Caribbean](#); Archives for Black Lives, [Anti-Racist Description Resources](#) (2019).

²⁶ Taken from Archives for Black Lives, [Anti-Racist Description Resources](#) (2019), p. 4.

- Who owns the data (legally) and is there consent for data archiving and sharing at the same time?

FAIR

- Can your data be reused in the future?
- Is your metadata and data open access thereby ensuring widest usability and impact?

Reproducibility

- Is your work reproducible?

What are good practices in relation to this task?

- Prioritise access for owners of the data and affected communities.
 - For example, Surinamese data housed in the Netherlands needs to be accessible for Surinamese citizens.²⁷
- Consider practical elements of accessibility.
 - For example, if your data is only accessible via a computer, this impacts the types of users you reach.
- Ensure your published data is FAIR.
- Offer your datasets in a format best suited to your audience or in multiple formats, such as csv and excel.

Resources

- FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP): <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>
- RDM Kit Advice on Data Publication: https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_publication
- Viktoria Brüggemann, Mark-Jan Bludau, Marian Dörk (2025). Laying it all out: Collage as a co-creative method for designing collection interfaces: <https://uclab.fh-potsdam.de/publications/laying-it-all-out-collage-as-a-co-creative-method-for-designing-collection-interfaces>

²⁷ From conversation with Margo Groenewoud.